

Theoretical study on the influence of formamide on the optical rotation of 2-amino-propanamide

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Abstract : Five stationary points of formamide-2-amino propionamide complexes have been optimized at the B3LYP/6-311++G (2d,2p) level and at MP2/6-31+G (d,p) level in the gaseous phase. Through analyzing conformers, the structure parameters, energies and important parameters were given out. We have found that the influences of formamide on the optical rotation of 2-amino-propanamide are large. This provides theoretical predictions for profound study on the optical rotation in the future.

Keywords : Density function theory, 2-amino-propanamide, formamide, optical rotation.

Introduction

The specific optical rotation, a parameter characterizing the natural optical activity, depends strongly on the conformation of the molecule. The conformations of amino acids have been a subject of increasing study due to their potential relationship to the structure of large peptides. Microwave spectroscopy, electron diffraction, and matrix isolation infrared spectroscopy have shown that multiple conformations of an amino acid may be detected experimentally¹⁻⁴. As a basic derivative of alanine, alaninamide is of great significance in the interstellar studies and biochemistry because amide derivative may also serve as simple models for *N*-terminal amino acids in peptides. Lavrich has calculated three conformers of alaninamide at MP2/6-31+G** level and studied them using the rotation spectra⁵. Formamide that usually chosen as the backbone of proteins to study the biological systems exhibiting the peptide type of bonding complex has been selected in the present paper along with 2-amino-propanamide. 2-Amino-propanamide has chiral, we can compare its optical rotation to identify its property change.

So it is significant to study optical rotation in the medical

field. In this paper, we have investigated six conformers of alaninamide at B3LYP/6-311++G (2d,2p) level, and for the comparison we have also optimized them at MP2/6-31+G (d,p) level.

Alanine has a chiral center in the molecule, so its derivative also has chiral center. For this reason, we have studied its optical rotation^{6,7}. The optical activity of chiral organic molecules was discovered nearly 200 years ago, and the phenomenon receives a wide use in characterizing those compounds⁸. Because of the chiral nature of the building blocks of living matters, optical phenomena associated with chirality constitute an important topic in physical chemistry. The lowest-order phenomenon in the transparent region is a natural optical activity, i.e. the optical rotation of the polarization plane of a linearly polarized light after transmission through a sample of chiral molecules^{9,10} and is therefore in principle a sensitive tool for structural investigations. However, this sensitivity makes the correlation between the optical rotation and the electronic and geometrical structure a difficult task. Even for a rigid molecule, a seemingly small perturbation such as changing the solvent may be beyond the

extent of reversing the sign of the rotation. Pecul^{11,12} studied the conformation dependence of the optical rotation of the amino acid (alanine, proline, serine and cysteine). Optical rotation calculations are very sensitive to the computational method and also the basis set¹³ that we select in computation. Stephens *et al.*¹⁴ showed that the B3LYP-correlated hybrid functional combined with suitable large basis sets yielded reliable results for rigid system. So in calculation of the specific optical rotation, the size of the basis set converges at aug-cc-pvdz and 6-311++G (2d,2p). And for comparison we have calculated the optical rotations at the basis sets of 6-31+G* and 6-311++G (d,p). In this paper we use the density function theory as primary computational method. The density functional theory (DFT) has become a popular tool in the computational chemistry.

Many studies have shown that the nonlocal hybrid functional B3LYP method has been applied successfully to the medium-sized molecules. There is a good example that Barone *et al.*¹⁵ has ever found that the B3LYP hybrid approach can give results close to the most sophisticated Hartree-Forck methods in a fraction of the computational time through the comparisons with the high-level results of Csaszar¹⁶.

Computational methods :

The frequency of yellow sodium D-line^{17,18} is always used in experimental measurements. We have calculated the molar rotation values at a frequency 589.3 nm. The optical activity tensor is related to the (imaginary) electric dipole-magnetic dipole polarizability tensor $G(-\omega, \omega)$ which for a frequency ω can be written in the length-gauge formulation as follow¹⁹⁻²¹ and the dipole-magnetic dipole polarizability tensor is given by the expression :

$$G'_{\alpha,\beta}(-\omega;\omega) = 2\omega Im \sum_{n \neq 0} \frac{\langle 0 | \hat{\mu}_{\alpha} | n \rangle \langle n | \hat{m}_{\beta} | 0 \rangle}{\omega_{n0}^2 - \omega^2} \\ = -Im \langle \langle \hat{\mu}_{\alpha}; \hat{m}_{\beta} \rangle \rangle \quad (1)$$

Here the sum runs over the excited-state manifold $|n\rangle$, $|0\rangle$ denotes the reference ω_{n0} state no indicates the excitation energy, and μ_{α} and m_{β} are the components of the electric and magnetic dipole operators, respectively. The optical-activity tensor is related to the parameters determining the electronic circular (ECD) spectra. The electric dipole-magnetic dipole polarizability can be associ-

ated with the optical rotatory strengths nR corresponding to the transitions from $|n\rangle$ to $|0\rangle$ through the relation :

$$G'_{\alpha,\beta}(-\omega;\omega) = 2\omega Im \sum_{n \neq 0} \frac{{}^nR}{\omega_{n0}^2 - \omega^2} \quad (2)$$

For a sample of randomly oriented molecules, the specific optical rotation $[\alpha]$ depends on the trace of the optical activity tensor $\beta = -\frac{e}{3} \frac{j}{\omega} \langle \langle \hat{d}'_{xx} + G'_{yy} + G'_{zz} \rangle \rangle$ in the following manner :

$$[\alpha] \approx 0.1343 \times 10^{-3} \cdot \beta \cdot \bar{\nu}^2 M^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where β is given in atomic units (bohr)⁴, $\bar{\nu}$ is the wave number of the incident radiation in cm^{-1} , and M is the molar mass in g mol^{-1} . The units of $[\alpha]$ are then given as $\text{deg cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1} \text{dm}^{-1}$.

All calculations have been performed using Gaussian 03 program package²².

Results and discussion

Geometries :

Five optimized conformers of complexes (2-amino propanamide and formamide) at B3LYP/6-311++G (2d,2p) level in the gaseous phase are shown in Fig. 1. The most interesting structural parameters including bond lengths, bond angles and dihedral angles, are listed in Table 1. As can be seen from Table 1, the bond lengths have no substantial changes for all the conformers. The largest deviation of bond lengths (C9-N11) is only 0.022 Å in the conformers, and the bond lengths (C7-H13) just change only 0.002 Å. We can find that the deviations of the bond angles among the five conformers are larger than those of the bond lengths. The largest deviation among all the conformers is the $\text{A}_{\text{C8C7N10}}$, which is up to 4.56°, and the others are not more than 2.41°. For the dihedral angles of all the conformers, for a molecule with a chiral center, the negative and corresponding positive angles may reflect the mirror-image features, and the structure parameters of the chiral molecule and its' mirror-image are all very similar but their dihedral angles are opposite to each other. For simplicity, in this work we haven't given the mirror-images of all the conformers. It can be seen from Table 1, that the deviations of the dihedral angles among the five conformers are very large, which indicate that the structure of a conformer depends on the

Fig. 1. Optimized conformers of complexes (2-amino-propanamide and formamide) in the gas phase at B3LYP/6-311++G (2d,2p)

values of the dihedral angles greatly. For example, the dihedral angles configurations 4 and 5 are larger than others, resulting in the dihedral angle of 2-amino-propionamide a major change, actually a difference of more than 100. The change of dihedral angle among another three conformations is small. This is due to the configuration of 4 and 5 and formamide form strong hydrogen bonds, the dihedral angle N10C7C9N11 greater changes remarkably. It indicates that the influence of the formation of hydrogen bonds on the dihedral is very large.

Interaction energy :

The total energy and their relative energies in various

configuration are shown in Table 3. The order of their relative stability is AF1 > AF3 > AF2 > AF5 > AF4. The most stable configuration is AF1. The relative energies of several configuration are 15.8055, 9.9296, 23.8579 and 20.5235 kJ/mol, respectively. AF4 possess the highest energy and the most unstable structure. The value of optical rotation is also changed largely.

Optical rotations :

The optical rotations of 2-amino-propanamide are studied in various configurations. In the calculation of its specific rotation, we still calculated according to the sodium D-line (wavelength of 589.3 nm), using the density

Table 1. The structure parameters of complexes (2-amino-propanamide and formamide) in the gas phase at B3LYP/6-311++G (2d,2p) level

Parameters	AF1	AF2	AF3	AF4	AF5
R _{C7C8}	1.531	1.530	1.531	1.532	1.529
R _{C7H13}	1.094	1.094	1.092	1.093	1.094
R _{C7C9}	1.535	1.538	1.532	1.538	1.535
R _{C9N11}	1.337	1.344	1.346	1.359	1.352
R _{C9O12}	1.236	1.229	1.230	1.219	1.222
R _{N10H17}	1.012	1.012	1.012	1.015	1.015
R _{N10H18}	1.012	1.013	1.013	1.019	1.015
R _{N11H19}	1.021	1.018	1.005	1.005	1.007
R _{N11H20}	1.007	1.006	1.007	1.004	1.014
A _{C8C7C9}	109.042	109.026	108.889	110.203	109.738
A _{C8C7N10}	110.065	109.960	110.278	114.330	109.774
A _{C9C7N10}	111.528	111.782	111.105	112.333	113.521
A _{H13C7N10}	112.780	112.751	112.238	112.238	111.494
A _{C8C7H13}	108.266	108.223	108.615	108.345	108.204
A _{C9C7H13}	104.962	104.896	105.547	104.554	103.861
D _{C8C7C9O12}	74.200	74.463	74.136	45.016	70.080
D _{N10C7C9O12}	-164.042	-163.756	-164.213	173.756	-166.677
D _{N10C7C9N11}	16.999	17.282	17.151	-6.409	12.368
D _{C8C7N10H18}	-157.936	-159.653	-151.055	-69.098	-179.539
D _{C8C7N10H17}	-38.602	-40.620	-33.399	47.160	-63.967
D _{C7C9N11H20}	-0.349	0.388	-2.926	-6.859	11.536
D _{C7C9N11H19}	177.821	177.227	179.144	-174.623	176.637
Dipole moment	2.0947	0.7573	1.7675	5.1157	6.2237

The units here : bond lengths (R) in angstrom (A), the bond angles and dihedral angles in degree and the dipole moments in Debye (D).

function theory B3LYP in each of the three base sets (6-311++G (2d,2p), 6-311++G (d,p), ang-cc-pvdz). For comparison, we also use HF/SCF method in the same group based on the calculated values of specific rotation, calculated result including specific rotation $[\alpha]$ and the optically active parameters are presented in Table 2. As mentioned above, the computation of the optical rotation is very sensitive to the computation level and the geometry of the compound. It can be seen that different conformers have different specific rotation values, and more importantly, for one conformer, when computed at different basis sets or different computation theories, the results of optical rotations are also quite different. From the Table 2, we can see that the B3LYP and HF calculation of the optical rotation obtained data on the varied widely and even have the opposite sign of the data. The same method of calculation and the selected basis set is not the same as the results obtained are different. Cheeseman²⁰ have even suggested that it is important that the basis set need diffuse functions to compute optical rotation, and referred to the base set 6-311++G (2d,2p) is a relatively efficient, and more economical option. Therefore, this basis set is mainly chosen by us.

Let us take the results of configuration AF4 as an example to analyze. First, the data of specific rotation are 144.47 and 141.53 at the base set 6-311++G (2d,2p)

Table 2. Specific rotation values of the complexes calculated using density functional theory (B3LYP) and Hartree-Forck (HF) at the different basis set (unit : deg [dm(g/cm³)]⁻¹)

	C1		C2		C3		C4		C5	
	$[\alpha]$	β								
B3LYP/6-31+G (d)	51.89	0.1624	42.80	0.1339	59.12	0.1849	127.53	0.3990	9.05	0.0283
B3LYP/6-311++G (d,p)	48.41	0.1515	40.70	0.1273	56.69	0.1774	141.47	0.4426	12.05	0.0377
B3LYP/6-311++G (2d,2p)	43.99	0.1376	37.28	0.1126	57.06	0.1785	144.53	0.4522	10.95	0.0343
HF/6-311++G (d,p)	28.90	0.0904	27.00	0.0845	-20.22	0.0632	37.29	0.1167	25.63	0.0802
HF/6-311++G (2d,2p)	28.48	0.0891	27.78	0.0869	-21.92	0.0686	36.56	0.1143	21.41	0.0669

Table 3. The total energy (E_{total} , hartree) and relative energies, free energies and relative free energies at B3LYP6-311++G (2d,2p) level (unit : kJ mol⁻¹)

	AF1	AF2	AF3	AF4	AF5
<i>E</i>	-473.97433	-473.96619	-473.967722	-473.963124	-473.96537
<i>G</i>	-473.84433	-473.83831	-473.840547	-473.83524	-473.83651
ΔG	0.0000	15.8055	9.9296	23.8579	20.5235
E_{rel}	0.0000	21.3716	17.3493	29.4214	23.5421

ΔG represents free energy of stationary conformers.

and 6-311++G (d,p), respectively, and the absolute deviation is only three degrees. At the basis set 6-31+G (d) the results are slightly larger at 14°. As mentioned above, the computation of the optical rotation is very sensitive to the computation level. However, it can be seen from Table 2, that the deviation in the results computed using HF method at different basis sets is much more, and some even change the signs of the optical rotation. From this point we can make a conclusion that the HF method must be less reliable than density functional theory.

It can be found that the specific rotation is very sensitive to the geometry of the molecule. As shown in Table 2, the optical rotations of configurations 4 and 5 were compared with other configurations. For comparison, the difference between the dihedral angles of configurations 4, 5 and other configurations are also very large. This is due to the fact that the configurations 4 and 5 of 2-amino-propanamide and formamide form a hydrogen bond (N10...H5), resulting in the C* atom of the -CONH₂ to have an impact on spatial location.

It is well known that the specific optical rotations obtained by theoretical calculations should have deviations from the literature or experimental values. This is because some possible conformers we haven't obtained; there may be some other reasons, including the theory of model itself or calculation errors. After all, the study on the relations between the molecular structure and the optical rotations still need us to do a lot for further research.

Conclusions :

The five configurations of complexes (2-amino-propanamide and formamide) are obtained at the B3LYP/6-311++G (2d,2p). Moreover, analyzing bond lengths, bond angles and dihedral angles, we have found that the bond lengths have no substantial changes for all the conformers. The deviations of the bond angles among the five conformers are larger than those of the bond lengths. The deviations of the dihedral angles among the five conformers are very large, which is due to the formation of hydrogen bond between 2-amino-propanamide and formamide (N10...H5).

The calculations and analysis of the specific optical rotations for all the conformers suggest the optical rotation is very sensitive to the computation level and the geometry of the complexes. We can conclude that the large enough basis set can get relatively more reliable results and the HF method must be less reliable than density functional theory.

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